

More information on the jumping spider *Mexcala rufa* G.W. Peckham & E.G. Peckham, 1902 (Araneae: Salticidae) from South Africa

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ABSTRACT: *Mexcala* G.W. Peckham & E.G. Peckham, 1902 is known from 22 species and is recorded mainly from Africa. Four species are known from South Africa. *Mexcala rufa* G.W. Peckham & E.G. Peckham, 1902 one of the species has been described from South Africa, with the type locality only given as Cape Colony. Little is known about the species and more information is provided, with notes on their morphology based on live photographs, behaviour, distribution, and conservation status.

Keywords: behaviour, biodiversity, conservation, geographic distribution, ant mimic, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

Mexcala G.W. Peckham & E.G. Peckham, 1902 is known from 22 species and is recorded mainly from Africa, with only one species known from Iran (World Spider Catalog, 2025). The four species known from South Africa are *M. elegans* G.W. Peckham & E.G. Peckham, 1903, *M. meridiana* Wesolowska, 2009, *M. quadrimaculata* (Lawrence, 1942) and *M. rufa* G.W. Peckham & E.G. Peckham, 1902. *Mexcala rufa* is a southern African endemic described from South Africa, with the type locality only given as Cape Colony. During the South African National Survey (SANSA), the species was recorded from several localities in the Northern and Western Cape. Records from iNaturalist show the species is also known from Botswana and Namibia and in South Africa from the North West province.

The species is only known from the male. In the revision of Wesolowska (2009) drawings of the palp and abdomen were provided. More information on their colour variation and morphology based on live photographs are provided with information on their behaviour, distribution, and conservation status is provided.

METHODS

Voucher specimens sampled during SANSA surveys are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC). Some of the photograph's SANSA requested for the SANSA Virtual Museum are shown here. Additional information from pictures taken by the public deposited in iNaturalist was exported from <https://inaturalist> on 30 May 2025.

TAXONOMY

Mexcala rufa G. W. Peckham & E. G. Peckham, 1902

Mexcala rufa Peckham & Peckham, 1902: 333 (m); Peckham & Peckham, 1903: 247; Prószyński, 1984: 83; Wesolowska, 2009: 176; Prószyński, 2017: 31.

Diagnosis: Male: TL: 7-8 mm. Female unknown. Carapace dark in some specimens with a blueish black tint (Fig. 1); a few black setae present in the eye-region; the clypeus and front of the chelicerae bearing some tiny white scale-like setae; on the clypeus setae are arranged in transverse rows, but on the chelicerae, scattered (Figs 3 & 9). Abdomen oval (Figs 7 & 8); dorsal surface dark and entirely covered with dense golden-yellow (Figs 2 & 3) to orange setae (Fig. 10); no setae are around the anterior border and spinnerets and in some specimens the abdomen with two spots medially without setae, which resemble the ant *Camponotus fulvopilosus* they are associated with (Fig. 17); several specimens observed in iNat without these dark spots (Figs 10, 14 & 15), this might be juveniles or females.

Figures 1–3. *Mexcala rufa* male. 1–3. Dorsal view. Credits: 1 & 3. Peter Webb from Jakkalswater. 2. Cecile Roux from Bitterfontein.

Figures 4–9. *Mexcala rufa*. 4–6. Male Palp. 7. Abdomen. 8. Male habitus. 9. Eye pattern, anterior view. Credits: 4–7. Wesolowska (2009). 8. Peckham G. W. & Peckham E. G. (1903). 9. Peter Webb.

Legs 4132, almost equal in stoutness, femora slightly thicker; legs and palpi are black, but as typical in *Mexcala* species, the tip of leg I white; legs I-IV and palp with white longitudinal bands of setae (Fig. 2), which reflects in the dark (Fig. 11).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL: Botswana, Namibia, South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA (Fig. 16)

Figure 16. Distribution records of *Mexcala rufa* in South Africa. Showing the SANSA distribution records of material housed in the National Collection of Arachnida and the locations of iNaturalist “Research Grade” observations of *M. rufa* exported from <https://www.inaturalist> on 01 June 2025.

Explanatory Note: Although species identifications on iNaturalist rely mostly on the often doubtful recognition of live specimens from photographs, some spider species, such as *Mexcala rufa*, present distinctive colour patterns, body shape, and other morphological characters that allow identification from photographs with reasonable certainty.

HABITAT

During SANSA surveys it was sampled from the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al*, 2024), Grassland (Haddad *et al*, 2013), Nama Karoo and Savanna (Foord *et al*, 2011) biomes (Fig. 16).

Figures 10–15. 10. Male with orange setae from Wolwekop Nature Reserve (Felix Riegel). 11. Male from Graaf-Reinet showing the white setae on the legs and palp reflex (Shelley Edwards). 12. Anterior view showing typical posture. 13. Showing markings on legs (Peter Webb). 14–15. Undescribed female from Mountain Zebra National Park (Felix Riegel).

LIFE STYLE

At least two Salticidae species, *Kima africana* and *Mexcala rufa*, are known to mimic and exhibit close spatial associations with *C. fulvopilosus* (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, in press). Fig. 17 illustrates the distribution records of *M. rufa* overlaid on an iNaturalist observation density heatmap of *C. fulvopilosus*, providing empirical support for the hypothesis that the mimic's survival is closely linked to the presence of its ant model. *Camponotus fulvopilosus*, the yellow-haired sugar ant, is widely distributed across arid regions of southern Africa. It inhabits rocky areas, nesting under rocks, bushes, and fallen trees. *Mexcala rufa* a free-living ground dweller is frequently found around nests of *Camponotus* ants.

CONSERVATION STATUS

Mexcala rufa is presently protected in the Kgalagadi Transfontier Park, Twee Rivieren, Anysberg Nature Reserve, Gamkaskloof Nature Reserve, Cederberg and Mountain Zebra National Park.

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Figure 17. Distribution records of *Mexcala rufa* in South Africa in relation to the occurrence of *Camponotus fulvopilosus*.

Figures 18–19. 18. *Camponotus fulvopilosus* ants sampled at Jakkalsdraai in the Northern Cape. 19. The immature *M. rufa* female sampled in the same area. Credit: Peter Webb.

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